

LÍNGUA

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COMUNICADOS

1. [Prof. Steffen Walter participa de encontro com estudantes do NIATS durante missão de trabalho internacional na UFU](#)
2. Participação da estudante Aline Victória Machado Silva no I Programa de Iniciação Tecnológica (PIT-HC-UFU/EBSERH)
3. Projeto de Lei para Pessoas com Doença de Parkinson é Aprovado em Uberlândia

Mais [+]

EVENTOS

- I Encontro Interdisciplinar para o Estudo da Dor da Universidade Federal de Uberlândia**
- VII Simpósio em Engenharia Biomédica**
- Webinar: Telemedicina - Inovação para melhor cuidar**

Mais [+]

LINKS IMPORTANTES

- NIATS no GitHub**
- Comunidade do NIATS na plataforma ZENODO**
- Rede Brasileira de Avaliação de Tecnologias em Saúde**
- Universidade Federal de Uberlândia**

Mais [+]

Prof. Steffen Walter participa de encontro com estudantes do NIATS durante missão de trabalho internacional na UFU

Aconteceu nesta terça-feira, dia 12 de março de 2024, um encontro de estudantes do NIATS com o Prof. Steffen Walter da Universidade de Ulm na Alemanha. O encontro ocorreu das 13:30 às 13:30 no anfiteatro do Bloco 1E da Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica, no campus Santa Mônica. Durante o encontro o Prof. Steffen Walter ministrou uma palestra sobre suas pesquisas na área do reconhecimento automático de dor e os estudantes do NIATS tiveram a oportunidade de apresentar suas pesquisas.

Além do Prof. Adriano de Oliveira Andrade e do Prof. Steffen Walter, os seguintes estudantes participaram do encontro: Ana Carolina Miziara (graduanda em Engenharia Biomédica), Luanne Cardoso Mendes, Camille Marques Alves, Ariana Moura Cabral, Pedro Henrique Bernardes Caetano, Letícia de Queiroz Martins, Eduardo de Moura Neto, José Renato Munari Nardo, Rodrigo Gomide Gonzaga, Sheida Mehrpour, Walter Rodrigues de Andrade, Maria Olivia Domingos Rezio Ramos, Leandro Rodrigues da Silva Souza e Alice de Oliveira Barreto Suassuna.

A participação do Prof. Steffen Walter nesse encontro aconteceu no âmbito de uma missão de trabalho internacional financiada pelo Projeto CAPES-PRINT UFU (P9-Tecnologias convergentes aplicadas à saúde e bem-estar). Durante a missão de trabalho o Prof. Steffen executou ações no âmbito de uma pesquisa internacional sobre a doença de Parkinson, que é coordenada pelo Prof. Adriano Andrade e apoiada pelo CNPq (Processos 442150/2023-7 e 302942/2022-0).

Resumo da palestra ministrada pelo Prof. Steffen Walter

Short CV: Prof. Steffen Walter has carried out and published preliminary work in the field of automated content analysis of psychotherapy conversations. Since 2008, he has been involved in several projects concerning the optimization of so-called "affective computing"/ "automated pain recognition", in which the recognition of emotions and pain is investigated multimodally (biosignals, video, paralinguistics). Machine learning methods are used to classify basic emotions or valence/arousal and pain intensities. The BioVid, SenseEmotion and X-ITE datasets - which offers the possibility of training algorithms for pain and emotion recognition - were recorded by Walter and are used by working groups worldwide to optimize machine learning.

Title: Automated Pain Recognition - Where we are and where we want to go: A perspective

Pain typically is measured by patient self-report, but self-reported pain is difficult to interpret and may be impaired or in some circumstances not possible to obtain. For instance, in patients with restricted verbal abilities such as neonates, young children, and in patients with certain neurological or psychiatric impairments (e.g., dementia). Additionally, the subjectively experienced pain may be partly or even completely unrelated to the somatic pathology of tissue damage and other disorders. Therefore, the standard self-assessment of pain does not always allow for an objective and reliable assessment of the quality and intensity of pain. Given individual differences among patients, their families, and healthcare providers, pain often is poorly assessed, underestimated, and inadequately treated. To improve assessment of pain, objective, valid, and efficient assessment of the onset, intensity, and pattern of occurrence of pain is necessary. To address these needs, several efforts are being made in machine learning for automated and objective assessment intensity of pain from multimodal approach (bio-signal, video [face, mimic], voice [paralinguistic]) as a powerful alternative to self-reported pain.

Responsável / Responsible: Adriano de Oliveira Andrade

Email: adriano@ufu.br

Telefone / Phone: +55 34-3239-4729

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Title: Design and evaluation of a system for multi-modal automated pain recognition

Prof. Dr. Adriano O. Andrade
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Minas Gerais, BR

Prof. Dr. Steffen Walter
University Hospital Ulm
Department of Medical Psychology
Ulm, BW, Germany

1. Introduction

The diagnosis of pain in clinical medicine, as well as its measurement in human experimental research, is largely based on subjective assessments by patients. For many aspects of pain research and treatment this is insufficient and difficult, as Elliott [1] points out: "Measuring pain is probably one of the most challenging and difficult tasks in health sciences. Nilges specifies for research: "Pain measurement is the prerequisite for the diagnosis, treatment and scientific research of pain" [2]. However, the measurement of pain intensity in the field of medical and psychological diagnostics has so far only been solved to a limited extent, explicitly in people with limited communication skills (e.g. cognitive impairment / mechanical ventilation).

Since conventional pain measurement is based on subjective assessments, this leads to an uncertain pain diagnosis in people with verbal and/or cognitive impairments (e.g. people with dementia) and also in patients who are sedated and/or mechanically ventilated. However, only if an objective, reliable, valid and, in particular, temporally continuous pain diagnosis is possible, an appropriate treatment of the pathology causing the pain can be made possible, or pain treatment can be appropriately carried out with regard to the choice of analgesics, their dose, galenics, application interval and duration of application. A less valid measurement of pain can be used for misdiagnosis of the cause of the pain (inflammation, masses, etc.), reduced perfusion of the surgical area, depression, chronicity of pain and cardiovascular stress in patients at risk. On the other hand, high doses of painkillers are contraindicated, as they can lead to dependency and have undesirable side effects such as nausea, constipation, ulceration and gastrointestinal bleeding [3].

The goal in modern intensive care medicine is to treat an alert, cooperative (and therefore neurologically assessable) patient with adequate analgesia. In the past, analgesia together with deep sedation was used to create anesthesia-like conditions to provide vegetative shielding and Amnesia. From this it becomes clear that nowadays analgesia should be used very purposefully and that a recording of the individual pain level and the resulting need for analgesics is absolutely necessary. Many studies have shown an improvement in the overall and especially the cognitive outcome of intensive care patients with the concept of "**as much as necessary but as little as possible**" with regard to analgesia and sedation.

In the previous preparatory work (Figure 1) (video link: <https://www.jove.com/video/59057/multi-modale-signale-fr-die-analyse-von-schmerz-reaktionen-auf?language=German>) [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], multimodal signals were experimentally recorded in cooperation with the Centre for Innovation and Technology Assessment in Health of the Federal University of Uberlândia (NIATS - <http://www.niats.feelt.ufu.br/>) with the aim of selecting patterns that represent intensities from phasic vs. tonic or heat vs. electrical pain modalities. **Our vision is to use artificial intelligence techniques to continuously and objectively measure pain in patients with limited**

communication skills (Figure 2). This should enable improvements in the diagnosis and treatment of pain and its causes by supporting medical staff in pain assessment and at the same time relieving the strain on them.

Figure 1: Experimental stimulation (heat vs. electrical; phased), B: Test person during data acquisition, C: Multimodal signal path, D: Experimental infrastructure.

Figure 2: Simplified process of automated pain recognition.

2. Objectives

A monitoring system - in the form of a demonstrator - is to be developed (in NIATS, UFU, Uberlandia, Brazil), which will guarantee a valid recognition of pain in patients in an acute care environment. Signals for the detection and quantification of pain can have mimic, gestural, (psycho-)physiological and paralinguistic character. Pain-relevant parameters are recorded using non-invasive sensor technology, which records data on the (physical) reactions of the person in pain. This can be realized by a camera technology that records facial expressions, gestures or posture, while audio sensors record linguistics or paralinguistics. Physiological information can be derived via corresponding biopotential sensors (e.g. electrodes).

Physiological reactions

Pain almost always induces autonomic nervous processes in a person, which are operationalized by differentiated physiological signals and detected by sensors. Within the scope of the monitoring system presented, the following signals and sensor techniques are involved:

- Electromyography (muscle tone) of the facial muscles zygomaticus major and corrugator supercillii.
- Electromyography of the trapezius muscle or the electrocardiogram.
- Electrodermal activity (skin conductance) on the non-dominant hand.
- Breathing through a chest / abdominal belt with piezo element.
- Temperature changes in the peripheral extremities by a temperature sensor.

Behavioral reactions

Behavioral responses to pain perform two functions: protecting one's own body (e.g. through protective reflexes) and communicating the pain to the outside (e.g. as a request for help). The reactions are particularly evident in facial expressions and gestures:

- The facial expressions (expressive behavior) are measured front and side by video signals.
- The recording of gestures (e.g., body movement).

Acoustic reactions

The measurement of paralinguistics (non-verbal language behaviour, e.g. sighing, groaning, wheezing) and linguistics is done by means of microphones, which are usually highly sensitive.

The recognition of pain is based on the automated, computer-aided extraction and selection of significant (pain) characteristics or patterns from the above-mentioned data. This is operationalized by the use of machine learning methods (e.g. neural networks, support vector machines, deep learning) from the field of artificial intelligence, which, after successful training/learning, provide a probabilistic, categorical or numerical assessment of pain, e.g. "no pain", "mild pain", "severe pain" or "pain of intensity 0" to "pain of intensity 10". The choice of procedure has a significant impact on the detection rate and depends heavily on the quality and granularity of the underlying data.

Since the beginning of 2023, work has been underway on the development of the demonstrator in NIATS (in cooperation between Andrade and Walter). The system includes the capability of measuring sound, heartbeat, electromyography and skin conductance, which are useful parameters for the objective assessment of pain.

The first tests were carried out at NIATS in April 2023. First of all, the technical robustness will be tested: synchrony, data processing (filter methods) and algorithms etc. In particular, first experimental and clinical protocols will be prepared in order to submit an ethical proposal for the evaluation of the demonstrator.

Figure 3: Idealization of a graphical user interface of a pain monitoring system. A pain monitoring system should be able to provide the clinician with all relevant information (localization, quality, intensity, course) about the current pain of the patient in an effective presentation

Work schedule from 26.02. - 15.03.2024 of my stay in Uberlandia:

First of all, on Monday 26 February 2024, Prof. Adriano Andrade gave me an overview of the steps that have already been taken in the development of the prototype.

The overall development of the individual modalities: Biosignals, optics/video and paralinguistics is programmed in the development environment "Visual-Studio" with C++, the library is called "Armadilia". The biosignal processing (i.e. electrodermal activity, electromyography, electrocardiogram) has already been implemented. This includes the filter process and feature extractions. Furthermore, numerous interfaces have already been implemented. The interface is generated with "Wxwidgets". The interfaces for cameras have already been connected.

1. Visual Computing modality of prototype:

A key focus of my research stay was the integration of computer vision processing. This essentially consists of several steps.:

1.1. Annotation of the pain faces of 7 people from the BioVid Pain dataset (60 images per person; 20 baseline, 20 moderate pain, 20 pain tolerance):

The method FLAT-O: Facial Landmark Annotation Tool with OpenCV was integrated into Visual Studio for annotation. The programming language is Python.

Figure 4: Annotation of the faces

- Simple OpenCV GUI for **68-keypoint** facial landmark annotation.
- Annotate **more than one face per image**.
- For each feature (nose, eyes, eyebrows...) mark as many points as you like and the final **keypoints will be calculated automatically so that they are distributed evenly**. This means that you are not limited to a certain number of points per feature. You use as many as you need and the program will extract the correct number of keypoints for that feature
- Export the annotations in a single XML file, following the dlib's example XML file.

Figure 5: 64 landmarks

How to annotate with FLAT-O

Following packages:

- OpenCV
- Numpy
- Pandas
- Scipy

Once you have them installed, you just need to run this command:

```
python annotate.py -i path\to\your\images -x your\xml\folder
```

Make sure that all your images are in the same folder (path\to\your\images). By default, the program will split your data into training and test (10%). If you add the argument --no-splits it will only create one XML. The argument -t adjusts the test set size. This example sets the test set size to the 20%:

```
python annotate.py -i path\to\your\images -x your\xml\folder -t 20
```

Finally, you can change the display size with the argument -d. This example scales the images so that the largest dimension is 512 pixels long (but it won't affect the original images):

```
python annotate.py -i path\to\your\images -x your\xml\folder -t 20 -d 512
```

Remember that in order to train a shape predictor dlib requires the XML files (train and test) to be in the same folder as the images.

How to annotate eyes and lips

Eyes and lips are the only features that are closed shapes, and that would break the method I'm using for automatically spacing the keypoints. For that reason, I have separated the annotation of eyes and lips in many parts:

- Eyes
 - Upper eyelid:
 - Left: 37 to 40
 - Right: 43 to 46
 - Lower eyelid:
 - Left: [40, 41, 42, 37]
 - Right: [46, 47, 48, 43]
- Mouth
 - Outer
 - Upper lip: 49 to 55
 - Lower lip: [55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 49]
 - Inner
 - Upper lip: 61 to 65
 - Lower lip: [65, 66, 67, 68, 61]

This means that, in order to annotate the lower eyelids and lips properly, you will have to mark the edge points (i.e. 37, 40, 43, 46, 49, 55, 61, 65) twice.

Example

Let's suppose you are annotating the left eye:

- First, you mark the keypoints for the upper eyelid: 37, 38, 39 and 40.
- You press <space> and the final keypoints are generated.

- You move onto the next feature (lower eyelid) and mark the keypoints 40, 41, 42 and 37. However, when you press <space> again the keypoints 37 and 40 won't be overwritten because they were already saved in the previous part.

1.2 Feature implementation of the euclidean distance:

Euclidean distance features are calculated for the 68 points.

Figure 6: Model of the Euclidean distance

1.3 Creation of plots for pattern recognition:

Principal component analysis, biplots and finally a confusion matrix diagram were calculated.

Figure 7: eucDistPlot

Figure 8: PCAplot

Figure 9: Biplot

Figure 10: ConfusionChart

2. Interface between biopotential amplifier (BIOPAC) and the prototype:

An interface with the Biopac amplifier was created. This was initially done in MATLAB. This requires a so-called HAPI BIOPAC hardware API.

The BIOPAC Hardware API is a tool to permit third-party software programs to communicate with an MP160 or MP150 unit (Ethernet/UDP protocol), an MP36, or an MP35 for basic data acquisition. With the BIOPAC Hardware API, third-party software programs can communicate with an MP Device through a DLL using several API functions:

Figure 11: Infrastructure and signal plots

BIOPAC Hardware API BIOPAC Systems, Inc. www.biopac.com

Glossary

- API Application Programming Interface or Abstract Programming Interface: A set of routines, protocols, and tools for building software application; it hides the details and complexities of how things are done. A good API makes it easier to develop a program by providing all the building blocks. A programmer puts the blocks together. (Webopedia)
- DLL: Dynamic Link Library is a type of library commonly used in Windows environment; it uses the file extension ".DLL"
- Header File: Traditionally, serves as a manifest for what is in a source file(s) of programs written in C/C++ language; it uses the file extension ".h" Serves as a contract for programmers and does not contain all the details of the implementation.
- Library: A group of precompiled routines, methods, functions and objects that a program can use. It allows software developer to reuse code without revealing the implementation and source code.

What is included?

Programmers receive the files necessary to use the API as easily as possible:

- mpdev.dll
- mpdev.lib
- mpdev.h
- Documentation – preview reference manual
- Sample Browser
- Hardware Utilities
- Sample Programs* – download sample projects (C/C++ and LabVIEW samples)

Sample programs

C/C++ mp1XXdemo: Demonstrates basic usage of BHAPI's methods. C# Biofeedback: A simple biofeedback application that uses BHAPI. GoalKick: A simple game that uses BHAPI and a transducer as a human interface. MPCommander: A command line interface to the MP35, MP36 and the MP160/150 using BHAPI. TemperatureControl: A temperature control system using BHAPI, BIOPAC transducer and common electronic parts. VideoStimulus with MP35: A video stimulation application using BHAPI to acquire data from MP35 device. VideoStimulus with MP36: A video stimulation application using BHAPI to acquire data from MP36 device.

LabVIEW getBufferDemo with MP35: Demonstrates how to use BHAPI's getMPBuffer() function to acquire data from MP35. getBufferDemo with MP36: Demonstrates how to use BHAPI's getMPBuffer() function to acquire data from MP36. listAllMP150Demo: A VI that list all MP160/150s in the network startAcqDaemonDemo with MP35 device: Demonstrates how to use BHAPI's startAcqDaemonDemo() and receiveMPData() functions to acquire data from MP35. startAcqDaemonDemo with MP36 device: Demonstrates how to use BHAPI's startAcqDaemonDemo() and receiveMPData() functions to acquire data from MP36. temperatureDemo: A VI that monitors temp. and outputs voltage to a specified Analog Output given a threshold.

MATLAB mpdevdemo: Demonstrates basic usage of the BHAPI's methods.

VB .NET bhapibasics: Demonstrates the basic usage patterns of the BHAPI. FunctionGenerator: A program that transforms an MP device to an arbitrary waveform generator using BHAPI. ImageStim with MP35: An image stimulation program that acquires data from MP35 device using the BHAPI. ImageStim with MP36: An image stimulation program that acquires data from MP36 device using the BHAPI.

User requirements

You must have programming knowledge to use the BIOPAC Hardware API. The BHAPI is a development tool and it will require programming on the part of the customer.

System Requirements

- OS: Windows 10, 8.1, 7
- NET Framework (for the sample browser)
- MP160/150: Ethernet/UDP protocol supported. For DLC, firmware upgrades may be required; USB not supported; generates communication errors.
- To update firmware, set scaling, etc.: contact BIOPAC

3. Parkinson experiment „Object Tracking and Pattern Extraction From Drawings of People with Parkinson’s Disease Through Machine Learning“, UFU (NIATS):

I assisted in the Umbrela Parkinson's project of the NIATS. I was also a test subject in the control group.

4. Meeting with NIATS-students:

At the beginning I presented my own research work (approx. 25 min). The topic of my presentation was to give an overview of "Automated Pain Recognition", which concerned my own research work (approx. 25 min). The presentations mainly concerned

On 12.03.24 from 13:30 - 17:00 the students of NIATS (Centro for Innovation and Technology in Health) presented their study projects, i.e. Bachelor, Master and PhD theses. Each presenter has 12 minutes time.

Figure 12: The NIATS-Group around Prof. Dr. Adriano Andrade; right: My talk

Left back: Rodrigo, Eduardo, Jose Renato; In front: Luanne, Camille, Pedro; Right: I and Adriano; Desktop: Leandro, Alice

Appendix of Picture:

Figure 13: I in Bloco 1E